

Live Coding for Lighting Control and Musical Expression with Lighting

Noriki Amano

School of Human Environmental Sciences, Department of Informatics and Methodology,
Mukogawa Women's University
amnrk@mukogawa-u.ac.jp

ABSTRACT

We are studying live coding and are exploring its potential. As part of this, we designed and developed a system that controls the lighting equipment for stage production, and made it possible to link with Sonic Pi, a live coding system for music. Furthermore, we tried to express music by lighting (light irradiation) of lighting equipment. This research is unique not only in that it introduces a new domain of control systems to conventional live coding, which is mainly concerned with real-time generation of music and video, but also in that it integrates them. This research will enable live coders in the music field to perform music and at the same time create their own stage effects with lighting equipment. This means that the performer of the music can simultaneously perform and direct the stage. It is very significant to be able to stage performances that directly reflect the intentions of the performers.

1. INTRODUCTION

In live coding as performing art, coding is performed to improvise the generation of music and video. In this process, the coding performed by the live coder on stage looks like a live music performance. In some cases, the coding process is simply projected onto a screen, but in other cases, lighting equipment is used to create a stage production, just like a live music concert.

The role of staging equipment on stage is no small thing in live music performances. Staging effects such as light and smoke affect the impression of music, and depending on how they are staged, they can either enhance or detract from the image of the music.

We are exploring live coding as a performing art. As part of this, we designed and developed a system to control the lighting equipment for stage production, and linked it with Sonic Pi, a music-based live coding system, to enable flexible control of the lighting equipment itself by live coding. Furthermore, using this, we tried to express music by lighting (light irradiation) of lighting equipment. This research will enable live coders in the music field to perform music and at the same time create their own stage effects with lighting equipment. This means that a music performer can perform and direct the stage at the same time.

The structure of this paper is as follows: In section 2, we describe live coding as a performing art and lighting equipment as the background of this research. Based on this, we show our objectives and basic approaches of this study in Section 3. Then, in section 4, we describe the outline and implementation of the prototype system, and the expression of music using this system is described in section 5. Furthermore, we discuss related study in Section 6 and provide a summary in Section 7.

2. RESEARCH BACKGROUND

2.1 Live Coding

Live coding as a performing art has been performed all over the world since 2000. Live coding events such as Algorave[1] have been held in many places, mainly by TOPLAP[2], a live coding community led by Alex Mclean and other pioneers of live coding. In the academic world, international conferences such as ICLC[3] have been held annually since 2015.

Live coding as a performing art is dominated by coding performances where music and video are improvised and generated. In particular, live coding of music is a popular performance because it is easy to accept as similar to a live music performance, and has a long history.

Many tools for live coding as such a performing art have been developed in the past. Specifically, there are music live-coding tools such as Chunk[4], OverTune[5], TidalCycles[6], and Sonic Pi[7], as well as video live-coding tools such as Fluxus[8], LiveCodeLab[9], and Hydra[10]. The tools for live coding are necessarily interpreter-type systems due to the purpose of improvisation (live). In other words, it should not be a mere execution of a program, but a dynamic addition or change of a program to a running program, and the change should be immediately reflected in the execution of the program.

2.2 Lighting Equipment for Stage Production

In live music performances and concerts, a variety of stage production devices are used. Such stage production equipment includes lighting equipment, smoke machines, and sparklers. Among them, many types of lighting equipment, such as par lights, spotlights, and moving lights, are used for different purposes. In such lighting devices, moving lights (Figure 1) have superior features in terms of function and flexibility compared to other lighting devices.

- The position of the light beam can be changed flexibly.
- It can change the intensity of the light.
- Built-in multiple light colors in addition to white light color.
- Built-in multiple gobos (light patterns and pictures).

The moving light is literally a movable light, which can flexibly change the light irradiation position by setting the horizontal angle (pan angle) and vertical angle (tilt angle). Then by setting the light intensity, the brightness can be changed flexibly. In addition to white, multiple light colors such as red, blue, yellow, green, light blue, purple, and pink are built-in, and they can be changed flexibly, and a light pattern / pattern called gobo is built-in. From the above, the moving light alone can cover the production on the stage considerably.

Stage production equipment is often manually operated by connecting it to a dimming console with many faders via cables. However, in recent years, it is often controlled by software. As for the control software for lighting equipment, there are some such as DASLIGHT [11], but in many cases, such control software only realizes an operation table as software, and the user interface is almost the same as a physical dimmer console.

Figure 1. Moving light

Figure 2. Movable control of moving light

3. OUR OBJECTIVES AND BASIC APPROACHES

3.1 Our Objectives

We are exploring the possibilities of live coding as a performing art. As mentioned above, live coding as a performing art is mainly related to the generation of music and video, and there are few examples of other than those. Moreover, in this research, we placed the utmost importance on the

fact that it could be a performing art, and assumed that it would be live coded on stage. Based on the above, the goals of this study were set as follows:

- We enable live coding of lighting equipment.
- We make it possible to work with a live coding system for music.

Specifically, we are developing a live-coding system that controls lighting equipment and can be linked to a live-coding system for music. We select a moving light as a lighting device, and its moving parts can be moved flexibly by coding, and the light color and amount can be controlled. The aim of this project is to make it possible to produce a performance on stage by live coding of these moving lights, and to make this live coding itself a performance.

The point to be noted is that it is not to realize live coding for music itself. As mentioned in the previous section, there are many live coding systems for music, and rather than creating a system that competes with them, we sought a way to create a unique system that is independent of them and works with the existing ones, so that both can make the most of their strengths.

We would also like to emphasize that the physical device is controlled by live coding. This attempt to achieve performing arts through live coding of control systems is very unique. The reason why we chose the moving lights used on the stage as the target of control was because we considered their affinity with performing arts, and we aimed to make them a performing art even when they were not linked to live coding of music.

3.2 Our Basic Approaches

In this research, we will enable live coding of moving lights. The basic policy is as follows:

- Lighting on/off control
- Pan control: horizontal rotation
- Tilt control: Vertical rotation
- Light color control: Light color change
- Light intensity control: Light intensity change
- Enables cooperation with live coding systems for music

First, we enable the moving lights to be turned on and off. This includes blinking. Next, we enable horizontal rotation. This makes it possible to irradiate light in a circle around the moving light. Similarly, we enable vertical rotation. The vertical direction cannot be rotated 360 degrees like the horizontal direction, but it can be rotated 180 degrees. By controlling the pan and tilt in this way, it is possible to irradiate a hemispherical area such as a dome (Figures 2 and 3).

Light color and light intensity can also be controlled. Most of the moving light models have built-in colors other than white light. In addition, many moving lights can be adjusted for light intensity. From the above, it is possible to realize a light performance using various colors and their shades.

The point as important as the control of the moving light is the cooperation with live coding systems for music. In other words, the control of the moving lights is implemented as an independent system, which can be linked to live coding system for music.

4. IMPLEMENTATION

4.1 Prototype system configuration

In this study, we developed a prototype system for controlling the moving lights and a live coding system that works in conjunction with this system. The system configuration is as follows (Figure 4).

We use Processing[11] to control the moving lights. We also select Sonic Pi as the live coding system for music. Although Sonic Pi is a relatively new system for live coding of music, we emphasized the fact that the system is easy to install and can considerably lower the hurdle for trying live coding of music. While Sonic Pi does not have the tone of a full-fledged system like TidalCycle, it is simple and easy to use in terms of user interface.

Figure 4. Irradiation area of moving light

Figure 3. Configuration of the Prototype System

The live coding system is built on Sonic Pi, and part of it uses Ruby [12], which is the implementation language of Sonic Pi. OSC[13] communication is used to control the moving lights by live coding. The Sonic Pi supports OSC communication, and this linkage is achieved with a simple implementation.

For the moving light, we use the INNO POCKET SPOT [14] from ADJ (Figure 1). The INNO POCKET SPOT [14] is a standard moving light and is a DMX512 [15] standard product. The DMX512 signal of the moving lights is slightly different depending on the model. Therefore, to control other companies' moving lights using our prototype system, it is necessary to modify the code slightly. However, since the basic signals are almost the same, it is easy to modify the code.

4.2 Live Coding of Lighting Control

In this section, we explain the live coding of the moving lights. Live coding is done on Sonic Pi. The program is written in the Sonic Pi workspace in the same way as the Sonic Pi program, and executed by pressing the Run button (Figure 5). The first step in live coding of lighting control is to read the definition file (dmx.rb) using the require function of the Ruby language.

The definition file contains the instructions required for live coding of the moving lights and other information. The instructions to control the moving lights are as follows (Table 1).

TABLE 1. Moving light control commands (partial)

Command	Content
lt	Lighting on/off control
hn	Pan (horizontal angle) control
vr	Tilt (vertical angle) control
ps	Simultaneous pan / tilt control
cl	Light color control
dm	Light intensity control
gb	Gobo control

Figure 5. Live coding in conjunction with Sonic Pi

- Control code for lighting on/off, etc.:

```
lt onn    #Lighting on
lt off    #Lighting off
lt blk    #Blinking
lt fin    #Fade-in
lt fout   #Fade-out
```

- Control code for pan (horizontal angle: 0-540):
 hn 10 #Rotate 10 degrees
 hn 999 #Rotate random degrees
- Control code for tilt (vertical angle: 0-180):
 vr 150 #Rotate 150 degrees
 vr 999 #Rotate random degrees
- Simultaneous control code for pan and tilt:
 ps 10 20 #Pan 10, Tilt 10 degrees
 ps 999 20 #Pan random, Tilt 20 degrees
 ps 10 999 #Pan 10, Tilt random degrees
 ps 999 999 #Pan and Tilt random degrees
- Control code for light color:
 cl red #Lights up in red
 cl r # Lights up in random color

The light color is limited to the colors supported by the moving light used (7 colors: red, orange, yellow, green, blue, aqua, and pink). Regarding the control of light color, commands such as lighting two colors at the same time and changing from one color to another are also implemented, but they are omitted in this paper due to space limitations.

- Control code for light intensity: 0-100
 dm 0 # Maximum light intensity
 dm 100 # Minimum light intensity
- Control code for gobos:
 gb 1 #Gobo pattern 1 (1-7)
 dm 999 #Gobo pattern random

By combining the above instructions, for example, the following live coding can be realized.

```
require 'C:/SonicPi/dmx.rb'
lt onn #Lighting on (default: white)
cl red #Set the light color to red
hn 180 #Rotate 180 degrees (Pan)
cl r #Set the light color to random
vr 90 #Rotate 90 degrees (Tilt)
gb 5 #Set the gobo pattern 5
lt blk #Blink with gobo pattern 5
```

The above coding results in the following behavior.

“ After drawing a semicircle in the horizontal direction with red light, draw a 90-degree arc in the vertical direction with a random color, and display a blinking gobo pattern 5 directly above it. “

The above is an example of live coding specialized only for moving lights. By mixing this with the Sonic Pi coding, the moving light can operate in conjunction with the music.

```
require 'C:/SonicPi/dmx.rb'
lt onn #Lighting on (default: white)
play 60 #Make "C" sound (MIDI note 60)
cl red #Set the light color to red
play 62 #Make "D" sound (MIDI note 62)
```

```

cl orange    #Set the light color to orange
play 64     #Make "E" sound (MIDI note 64)
cl yellow   #Set the light color to yellow
lt off      #Lighting off

```

The above coding results in the following behavior.

“After the light turns on (white color), play the sound of "C" to change the light color to red, then play the sound of "Re" to change the light color to orange, then play the sound of "Mi" to change the light color to yellow and turn off the light.”

The above is equivalent to changing the light color of the moving lights according to the sound played, but from a different viewpoint, it can be thought of as expressing (visualizing) sound with moving lights.

5. MUSICAL EXPRESSION BY LIGHTING

5.1 Colorization of Sounds and Expression of Musical Scales

As mentioned in section 3.1, collaboration with live coding for music is one of the goals of this research. If we further promote the mixing of music codes and moving light control codes as discussed in the previous section, we will eventually reach the expression of music through lighting.

In our previous work [15], we have proposed a method for colorization of sounds. Concretely speaking, we proposed a method for colorization of sounds, which is based on an example of synesthesia. This is a colorization that maps rainbow colors to musical scales, and we used this rainbow color-based colorization of music as a reference for the expression of music by lighting in this study. However, there are some differences because the moving light we used did not support all seven colors of the rainbow.

TABLE 2. Colorization of Sound

C	D	E	F	G	A	B
Red	Orange	Yellow	Green	Aqua	Blue	Pink

The above shows the colorization of the sounds in this study (Table 2). The above colorization is almost the same as the colorization based on an example of synesthesia that we employed in our previous study, except that the "B" is pink instead of purple. This colorization was chosen because the moving light used in this project does not support the purple light color. Some models of moving lights differ in this respect, and it is possible to assign purple to "B" in some models.

In addition, the expression of semitones such as # (sharp) and b (flat) is to turn on two light colors at the same time. Although the moving light used in this study supports only the above 7 colors, it can output 2 colors at the same time (Figure 6).

Figure 7. Colorization of Semitones

Figure 6. Spiral expression of musical scales

TABLE 3. MIDI note number

	Gs	A	As	B	C	Cs	D	Ds	E	F	Fs	G
7	92	93	94	95	96	97	98	99	100	101	102	103
6	80	81	82	83	84	85	86	87	88	89	90	91
5	68	69	70	71	72	73	74	75	76	77	78	79
4	56	57	58	59	60	61	62	63	64	65	66	67
3	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	52	53	54	55
2	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42	43
1	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31

In addition to the above, we decided to use the spiral expression of musical scales adopted in our previous research for the pitches of notes. Specifically, it is a method of expressing sounds by arranging them in a spiral. For example, for the note "C", the "C" one octave higher is located at the upper of the spiral than the "C" one octave lower (Figure 7).

Such a spiral expression of the scale has a good affinity with the movable range of the moving light (Figure 3). This is combined with the colorization of sound to increase the brightness according to the pitch (Figure 8). For example, in the case of "C," sound the "C" one octave higher and the "C" one octave lower have the same red color, but the former is brighter than the latter, resulting in a brighter red color. In terms of coloration, the higher notes are lighter and the lower notes are darker.

5.2 Wrapper Functions

In this research, we have implemented a wrapper function on the Sonic Pi to realize the expression of music through lighting described in the previous section. A wrapper function is one that wraps around the internal code to provide a function. In other words, using the wrapper function implemented in this research, it is possible to control moving lights with colors and movements that match the music as if writing a Sonic Pi music program.

From now, we explain about the wrapper function using simple Sonic Pi program in detail.

```
play 60      # Make "C" sound (MIDI note 60)
```

The above is the simplest Sonic Pi program, and when executed, it will produce a "C" sound. However, "C" also has high and low notes. As it turns out, this one is designed to play the "C" of the fourth octave. On a piano keyboard, this corresponds to the middle "C". The number of 60 is called the note number in the MIDI[17] specification for electronic instruments. These note numbers are defined as follows (Table 3). In Table. 3 above, the rows and columns represent octaves and note names, respectively. The number in each cell is the MIDI note number.

From the above, the wrapper function is implemented as follows.

```
def c(num)      # "C" sound
  cl red        # Light color is red
  hn 0          # Front side (Pan)
  if num == 1   # 1 octave
    play 24     # Play note number 24
    vr 15       # 90 degrees (Tilt)
    dm 20       # Brightness of light
  elsif num == 2
    ...         # Omission
```


Figure 8. Spiral expression and colorization of musical scales

```

elseif num == 7
  play 96
  vr 75
  dm 80
end
end

```

The above is a wrapper function for "C," and the main points are as follows.

- Sound: "C"
- Height of sound: 1 to 7 octaves (Table 3)
- Color: Red
- Brightness: 20-80 (10 per octave)
- Horizontal angle: 0 degrees (front side)
- Vertical angle: 15-75 degrees (10 per octave)

The wrapper functions described above are implemented for musical scale. An example of the use of the wrapper functions is shown below.

```

for i in 1..7 do
  c i
  sleep 1
end

```

The above code calls a wrapper function in a loop statement to realize the behavior of a moving light, changing the color of the light from dark red to light red while simultaneously rotating the vertical direction from 15 degrees to 75 degrees while sounding one "C" from the first octave to the seventh octave. This is an uninteresting coding example, but we actually coded a portion of Japanese nursery rhyme and other songs with a wrapper function to verify the operation of the moving lights (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Experiment of using a Japanese nursery rhyme (partial)

Figure 10. Experiment of a music with randomness

One of the most exciting aspects of live coding in the music field is the improvisational nature of the music and the introduction of randomness to create music that is not scheduled. The following is an example of how such randomness is incorporated into the control of moving lights (Figure 10).

```

live_loop :live do      # "C" sound
  c rrand(1, 7)        # Wrapper function(C)
  hn 999               # Pan degrees: random
  vr 999               # Tilt degrees: random
end

```

```
cl r          #Color: random
sleep 1      #Leave one beat
end
```

The above is a program that plays the "C" sound continuously, but the pitch of the sound, the horizontal and vertical directions of the moving lights, and the color are all set randomly. Furthermore, with the `live_loop` instruction, the program can be changed by continuing to code while playing the sound and moving the moving lights.

Chords are not implemented in the current prototype. When chords are played, the behavior of the moving lights is basically the same as that of a set of single note behaviors. For example, when C major is played, the action of "C", the action of "E", and the action of "G" are performed in that order. In other words, the action is the same as if the chords were played as a single note, "C," "E," and "G," but this is a subject for future work.

Unfortunately, this experiment was not conducted on stage. Although we recorded video footage as well as images, the experiment was conducted in an ordinary laboratory, and the video footage does not fit well with the staging. The images (Figs. 9 and 10) also fail to convey the atmosphere of live coding. In future experiments, we will carefully select the location. At present, we are considering experiments on stages and domes. By using commercially available cardboard domes, we would like to confirm the expression of music by lighting.

6. RELATED WORK

As mentioned in section 2.1, live coding as a performing art is mostly about the generation of music and images. They are not in competition with this research, but are complementary to it. In particular, this research has a good affinity with live coding for music, and is considered to be a promising area for future development. It is also possible to collaborate with live coding for video. If a part of the generated image is replaced with the control of light by moving lights, it becomes possible to generate a three-dimensional image. Tadokoro's work [16] is a good reference for such live coding as a performing art.

Trends and currents in live coding as a performing art can be found in the list of papers accepted to ICLC. As far as the previous papers are concerned, most of the topics are related to music and video. However, if we look it well, we will find that some of the research is not about the generation of music and video itself, but about their execution environment and interface. For example, we can find a research on live-coding environments in web browsers, etc. Recently, the generation of music and video through live-coding incorporating machine learning and deep learning has also attracted attention [18]. Although it is not an academic conference, there have been recent music-related events such as MUTEK [19], where high quality live coding performances can be seen.

7. CONCLUSIONS

In pursuit of live coding as a performing art, we have implemented a system that can flexibly control the lighting equipment (moving lights) for stage production and link it to the Sonic Pi live coding system for music. Furthermore, using this prototype system, we conducted a trial-and-error study on the expression of music by lighting. This research is distinct from related research in the following ways.

- Live coding on physical equipment
- An attempt to extend live coding for music systems

In addition, this research proposes a new type of performance that focuses on the lighting, which is only a supporting role on the stage as a staging device, and adds the position of "stage director" as a new expressionist to the music performer, presenting a new way of enjoying music performance to the audience.

Through this research, we would like to create an entertainment world in which music and stage direction are well-balanced, in which musicians create music with the "stage direction effect" in mind, and the audience looks forward to the "stage direction created by the music."

Acknowledgments

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